

JEFF-3.3 and CENDL-3.2 ^{56}Fe Nuclear data adjustment exercise based on shielding benchmark experiment

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ABSTRACT

Iron is an important structural material and shielding material in nuclear reactors, but there are still significant differences in the evaluation of $^{56}\text{Fe}(n, \text{inl})$ cross sections (neutron inelastic scattering cross section) in the latest evaluation files. In addition, shielding benchmark testing results show the performance of iron data in shielding calculation still needs to be improved. In order to improve the accuracy of shielding calculation and provide quantitative feedback for the nuclear data evaluation, JEFF-3.3 and CENDL-3.2 ^{56}Fe nuclear data were adjusted based on shielding experiments ASPIS-Iron88. **Sensitivity to ^{56}Fe elastic, inelastic and capture cross section was calculated using Monte Carlo code JMCT-2.0.** A nuclear data adjustment code named PyADJ was developed, using sensitivity and covariance data as input data, the nuclear data adjustment code PyADJ calculated adjustment factors for ^{56}Fe elastic, inelastic and capture cross section. Finally, the shielding benchmark ASPIS-Iron88 was recalculated to validate the adjusted ^{56}Fe nuclear data, the validation results showed that the accuracy of the shielding calculation has been significantly improved.

Keywords: nuclear data, adjustment, shielding benchmark, sensitivity analysis

1. INTRODUCTION

Stainless steel is an important structural and shielding material in reactors, with iron being the main component. Iron (Fe) has four natural isotopes, with abundances of ^{54}Fe (5.845%), ^{56}Fe (91.754%), ^{57}Fe (2.119%), and ^{58}Fe (0.282%), among which ^{56}Fe is the predominant one. The accuracy of iron's nuclear data is crucial for reactor shielding calculations. In nuclear data research, iron is one of the most closely watched nuclides, especially ^{56}Fe , apart from fuel nuclides. In the CIELO project of the International Project on Evaluation Cooperation (WPEC) organized by the OECD Nuclear Energy Agency (OECD/NEA), ^{56}Fe is listed as one of the five most important nuclides. In recent years, the International Nuclear Data Evaluation Network (INDEN) has been continuously updating the evaluated data of ^{56}Fe . However, there are still significant differences in the evaluation of the $^{56}\text{Fe}(n, \text{inl})$ (neutron inelastic scattering) cross-section in the latest evaluation libraries. In the energy region above 4MeV, difference between different evaluations is below 15%, while in the energy region below 4MeV, the difference in evaluation data between libraries is gradually exceeding 40%^[1]. In addition, shielding benchmark testing results show the performance of iron data in shielding calculation still needs to be improved. In the shallow penetration shielding benchmark testing represented by the IPPE^[2] experiment, the calculated neutron leakage spectrums still have a significant deviation from the experimental values. In the deep penetration shielding benchmark testing represented by the ASPIS-Iron88 experiment^[3], the calculated integral values even far exceed the uncertainty range of the experimental values. Therefore, the accuracy of ^{56}Fe nuclear data still needs to be further improved.

Improving experimental measurement techniques and nuclear reaction theories are the most important means to improve the accuracy of nuclear data, but these methods are costly in terms of economy, human resources, and time. Nuclear data adjustment utilizes existing experimental information to

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optimize nuclear data and obtain data that meet the accuracy requirements of numerical simulation calculations, which is an effective method with lower time and economic costs to improve the accuracy of nuclear data. Deep penetration shielding calculations have higher requirements for the accuracy of nuclear data. Adjusting nuclear data based on deep penetration shielding benchmark experiments can better improve the accuracy of nuclear data. Kodeli^[4] has conducted the adjustment exercise of ⁵⁶Fe nuclear data based on the deep penetration shielding benchmark experiment ASPIS-Iron88. In his work, the sensitivities of several reaction rates to ⁵⁶Fe elastic scattering, inelastic scattering, capture cross sections, and to **prompt fission neutron spectra** (PFNS) of ²³⁵U were calculated. The ACE format data of ⁵⁶Fe were adjusted and used to recalculate several reaction rates with MCNP code^[5], which showed a significant improvement in the accuracy. However, the sensitivities related to ⁵⁶Fe were calculated for only several thicknesses in the experimental block, accordingly the improvement was showed for only 4 positions in the experiment, and no further validation was performed for the adjusted nuclear data. In addition, the cross section sensitivity analyses were performed using SUS3D^[6] perturbation code, based on the direct and adjoint neutron flux moments calculated by the DORT code. The C/E values calculated using the MCNP and the DORT codes show a difference within ~15% indicating that the adjusted ACE format data still has a certain deviation from the optimal solution.

In this work, the Monte Carlo code **JMCT**^[7-9] was used to calculate the sensitivity to the ⁵⁶Fe nuclear data for all the reaction rates. In addition, further validation was performed for the adjusted nuclear data using the shielding benchmark experiment IPPE. The Section 2 of the article briefly introduces the nuclear data adjustment methodologies and codes. Section 3 provides a detailed account of the adjustment of ⁵⁶Fe nuclear data, covering the introduction and simulation of the shielding benchmark experiment, sensitivity analyses. Section 4 introduces the analysis of adjustment results and the validation of the adjusted nuclear data. Section 5 comes to the conclusion.

2. METHODOLOGIES AND CODES

The following computer codes were used for benchmark experiment calculations and the nuclear data adjustment analyses:

- Neutron transport calculations were performed using the Monte Carlo code JMCT-2.0^[8]. **JEFF-3.3**^[10] and **CENDL-3.2**^[11] cross sections data in the pointwise were used in the JMCT code, respectively, cross section sensitivity analyses were performed using JMCT-2.0;
- Cross section adjustment code PyADJ.

2.1. JMCT code

The shielding benchmark was modelled using the code JMCT, the integral parameters and sensitivity were both calculated in the simulation of JMCT. JMCT is a large-scale, high-fidelity, three-dimensional general neutron-photon-electron-proton transport Monte Carlo software system. JMCT is equipped with CAD modeling and visualizes the image output. It supports the geometry of the body and the structured/unstructured mesh. JMCT has most functions, variance reduction techniques, and tallies of the traditional Monte Carlo particle transport codes. Two energy models, multi-group and continuous, are provided. In recent years, some new functions and algorithms have been developed, such as Doppler broadening on-the fly (OTF), uniform tally density (UTD), consistent adjoint driven importance sampling (CADIS), fast criticality search of boron concentration (FCSBC) domain decomposition (DD), adaptive control rod moving (ACRM), and random geometry (RG) etc. The JMCT is also coupled with the discrete ordinate SN code JSNT to generate source-biasing factors and weight-window parameters. JMCT can be used to simulate reactor physics, criticality safety analysis, radiation shielding, detector response, nuclear well logging, and dosimetry calculations etc.

2.2. Cross section adjustment code PyADJ

The **PyADJ** code is mainly based on the Bayesian theory and the maximum a posteriori method. Assume the adjusted cross section C' and posterior integral quantities I' are the optimal estimates in the maximum likelihood sense, then the nuclear data and covariance before and after the adjustment, as

well as the integral quantities and covariance, should satisfy the maximum likelihood function as shown in Equation (1).

$$L = \exp \left\{ -\frac{1}{2} \left[\left(\frac{C' - C}{C} \right)^T M_r^{-1} \left(\frac{C' - C}{C} \right) + \left(\frac{I' - I_e}{I_e} \right)^T V_r^{-1} \left(\frac{I' - I_e}{I_e} \right) \right] \right\} \quad (1)$$

Where, **L is the maximum likelihood function**, C is priori cross section being adjusted, I_e is integral experimental data used to adjust C, I_c is calculated integral data based on C, S is the sensitivity data of I_c to C, M_r is the covariance data of C, V is the covariance data of I_e.

Based on the Generalized Linear Least Square method, the cross section adjustment factor can be expressed as follows.

$$\delta C = -\left(M_r S^T W^{-1} \right) d \quad (2)$$

Where, d is integral bias, $d = \left\{ d_j = \frac{i_c - i_e}{i_c}, \quad j = 1, 2, \dots, m \right\}$

$$W = S M_r S^T + F V_r F \quad (3)$$

F is diagonal matrix of I_e/I_c.

The PyADJ code is written in Python3 and consists of four modules: data reading, covariance matrix construction, nuclear data adjustment based on generalized least squares, and result output. It can generate SG33-formatted data file, including adjustment factors categorized by energy group and reaction type. The PyADJ code can be applied to multi-parameter adjustment, enabling simultaneous adjustment of nuclear data based on criticality, shielding, and kinetics experiments.

The following input data is needed for the adjustment:

- priori cross section being adjusted (C), which was taken from JEFF-3.3 and CENDL-3.2 respectively and processed by NJOY2016^[12] into the ACE format.
- cross sections' relative covariance matrix (M_r), which was taken from JEFF-3.3 and processed by NJOY2016 with 33 energy groups in this work,
- values of the experimental-to-calculated ratios (I_e/I_c), where, I_c was calculated using JMCT in this work,
- relative sensitivity matrix of the nuclear data (S), which was calculated using JMCT in this work,
- covariance matrix V_r of the experimental values I_e.

Correlations between the cross sections and the integral parameters are assumed to be zero. Then the adjustments are calculated by the formula (2).

3. BENCHMARK ANALYSES

3.1. ASPIS-Iron88 experiment simulation

Iron88 benchmark experiment was performed in 1988 in ASPIS shielding facility installed on the NESTOR reactor at Winfrith, to study the neutron transport for penetrations up to 67cm in steel. The benchmark experimental array irradiated in ASPIS is shown schematically in side elevation in Figure 1. It comprises a fission plate made of 93% enriched U-Al alloy driven by thermal neutrons from the NESTOR reactor and installed in front of the shield made from 13 mild steel plates and a deep backing shield manufactured from mild and stainless steel. Each plate is approximately 5.1 cm thick, 182.9 cm wide and 191.0 cm high. Absolute source strength and spatial distribution were determined by fission product counting and ⁵⁵Mn(n, γ) measurements over X-Y front surface. Au, Rh, In, S and Al activation foils were placed in 7.4-mm air gaps between each slab component along the fission plate axis at several shield thicknesses up to 67cm, **the positions of the foils are shown in Figure 1 as A1-A15. The neutrons leaking from the NESTOR core induce fissions in the fission plate, and the fission neutrons propagate into the shielding leading to activation in the activation detectors. The neutron source was measured**

all over the fission plate using manganese and sulphur detectors in order to determine the source's intensity and spatial distribution.

In this study, the simulation calculation of ASPIS-Iron88 experiment was carried out using the JMCT-2.0 Monte Carlo code with JEFF-3.3 and CENDL-3.2 respectively. Figure 2 shows the view of the JMCT modelling of the ASPIS-Iron88 experiment. Power normalization had been done for the **calculated results before compared with the experimental values**. Power normalization was conducted based on reactor power, fission power and the number of neutrons per fission of ^{235}U .

$$NORM = NP \times FP \times \bar{\nu} \times FpW / \text{barn} \quad (4)$$

Where, NORM is the normalization factor, NP is the NESTOR power of 30kW, FP is an absolute plate power of 5.68×10^{-4} Watts per NESTOR Watt, FpW is 3.121×10^{10} fissions per Watt, $\bar{\nu}$ is 2.437 neutrons per fission.

According to Kodeli's research^[4], the PFNS of ^{235}U has a significant impact on $^{27}\text{Al}(n,\alpha)^{22}\text{Na}$ reaction rate. Therefore, in this work, the adjustment factor for PFNS of ^{235}U calculated by Kodeli is directly adopted from the WPEC SG39 web page^[13] to adjust the source term in the input card of JMCT.

Figure 1 The view of ASPIS-Iron88

Figure 2 JMCT modelling of the ASPIS-Iron88

Figure 3 shows the comparison of the calculated and measured reaction rate distribution using the CENDL-3.2 transport cross section and the dosimetry cross section from IRDFF v1.05^[14].

Figure 3 C/E ratios for the reaction rates measured in the ASPIS-Iron 88 benchmark

Monte Carlo calculation based on CENDL-3.2 shows that, calculated reaction rates of $^{115}\text{In}(n,n')^{115m}\text{In}$ and $^{27}\text{Al}(n,\alpha)^{22}\text{Na}$ fall within the uncertainty range of the experimental values. Reaction rate of

$^{32}\text{S}(n,p)^{32}\text{P}$ is partially within the uncertainty range of the experimental values. The calculated reaction rates of $^{197}\text{Au}(n,\gamma)^{198}\text{Au}$ and $^{103}\text{Rh}(n,n')^{103m}\text{Rh}$ reactions show significant deviations from the experimental values, with the maximum deviation approaching 15%.

The results based on JEFF-3.3 cross section show that, calculated reaction rates of $^{115}\text{In}(n,n')^{115m}\text{In}$ and $^{27}\text{Al}(n,\alpha)^{22}\text{Na}$ fall within the uncertainty range of the experimental values. There is a significant deviation between the calculated and measured reaction rate of $^{32}\text{S}(n,p)^{32}\text{P}$, with the maximum deviation approaching 25%. The calculated reaction rates of $^{197}\text{Au}(n,\gamma)^{198}\text{Au}$ and $^{103}\text{Rh}(n,n')^{103m}\text{Rh}$ reactions show significant deviations from the experimental values, with the maximum deviation approaching 20%.

3.2. Sensitivity analyses

For ASPIS-Iron88 experiment, the main component of steel plates is iron, the nuclear data of ^{56}Fe has a significant impact on the calculated reaction rates. The sensitivity analyses of ^{56}Fe elastic, inelastic and capture cross section were therefore performed using JMCT-2.0. The 1-group sensitivity summed up from the 33-group sensitivity to ^{56}Fe elastic, inelastic and capture cross section are presented in Figure 4.

Figure 4 1-group sensitivity to the ^{56}Fe elastic, inelastic and capture cross-sections

The two calculations based on JEFF-3.3 and CENDL-3.2 give a similar behavior. For the $^{197}\text{Au}(n,\gamma)^{198}\text{Au}$ reaction rate, JMCT-2.0 calculations fail to converge for both elastic and inelastic scattering cross sections, the statistical errors are more than 5%. This can be explained by the complexity of the problem and compensation effects, as contrary to the neutron capture where a neutron is killed and therefore cannot contribute to the reaction rate anymore, scattered neutrons remain in the geometry and are slowed down, which makes them more sensible to the $^{197}\text{Au}(n,\gamma)^{198}\text{Au}$ reaction. The capture sensitivity is the most important for $^{197}\text{Au}(n,\gamma)^{198}\text{Au}$ reaction rate, the sensitivity increases rapidly in the first 5cm penetration thickness and then reach an asymptotic behavior in deeper positions. The sensitivity to elastic and inelastic scattering varies with the penetration thickness in an irregular pattern due to the un-convergence. For the $^{103}\text{Rh}(n,n')^{103m}\text{Rh}$ reaction rate, the sensitivity to elastic and inelastic scattering presents a similar but less obvious un-converged behavior after around 30cm of deep propagation. For the $^{32}\text{S}(n,p)^{32}\text{P}$ reaction rate, sensitivities have been obtained with JMCT-2.0 for all the studied reactions. The convergence in this case can be explained by two reasons: first, $^{32}\text{S}(n,p)^{32}\text{P}$ is a threshold reaction, neutrons are killed by the code when they are slowed down below the 900keV threshold, allowing for

a larger number of simulated histories than for $^{197}\text{Au}(n,\gamma)^{198}\text{Au}$ reaction which doesn't have a threshold. Second, the neutrons scattered by ^{56}Fe are slowed down and therefore are more likely to go below the 900keV threshold and not to contribute to the reaction rate anymore. The elastic scattering sensitivity of $^{32}\text{S}(n,p)^{32}\text{P}$, $^{115}\text{In}(n,n')^{115\text{m}}\text{In}$ and $^{103}\text{Rh}(n,n')^{103\text{m}}\text{Rh}$ give the similar behaviors. However, the values obtained for the $^{32}\text{S}(n,p)^{32}\text{P}$ are the highest because the last sulphur detectors are further from the neutron source than the indium and rhodium detectors, the sensitivity increases with the neutron penetrate thickness, the further the distance, the higher the sensitivity. In addition to this, the threshold of the studied reaction is very high, for example, a neutron with an energy of 2 MeV (mean energy for a fission neutron) would be pushed out of the energy range of the reaction by only 20 elastic collisions on ^{56}Fe . The $^{32}\text{S}(n,p)^{32}\text{P}$ reaction rate presents the highest sensitivity to inelastic scattering sensitivity among all reaction rates. Its (n,p) threshold (900 keV) is higher than for the $^{103}\text{Rh}(n,n')^{103\text{m}}\text{Rh}$ (40 keV) and $^{115}\text{In}(n,n')^{115\text{m}}\text{In}$ (300 keV), the threshold of inelastic scattering of ^{56}Fe is slightly below the $^{32}\text{S}(n,p)^{32}\text{P}$ threshold. The sensitivity to the ^{56}Fe capture of $^{32}\text{S}(n,p)^{32}\text{P}$, $^{115}\text{In}(n,n')^{115\text{m}}\text{In}$ and $^{103}\text{Rh}(n,n')^{103\text{m}}\text{Rh}$ is about 100 times smaller than the sensitivity to the inelastic scattering respectively. For the $^{27}\text{Al}(n,\alpha)^{22}\text{Na}$ reaction rate, the sensitivity to ^{56}Fe inelastic scattering is the most important one. The sensitivity increases rapidly in the first 5cm and then reach an asymptotic behaviour in deeper positions. The sensitivity to the elastic scattering of ^{56}Fe is positive at most positions, this sensitivity decreases with propagation and becomes negative at 25cm. the capture sensitivity is even lower than the elastic scattering sensitivity.

4. ADJUSTMENT RESULTS

4.1. recalculation of ASPIS-Iron88 experiment

Relying on the calculated and measured reaction rates, sensitivity to ^{56}Fe elastic, inelastic and capture cross section, JEFF-3.3 covariances for ^{56}Fe elastic, inelastic and capture cross section, and the measurement uncertainties for the ASPIS-Iron88 benchmark. The code PyADJ accomplished the adjustment for ^{56}Fe elastic, inelastic and capture cross section. The ASPIS-Iron88 benchmark was recalculated based on the adjusted nuclear data. Figure 5 shows the comparison of the calculated and measured reaction rate distribution before and after adjustment based on JEFF-3.3 and CENDL-3.2, respectively.

Figure 5 comparison of C/E ratios before and after adjustment of ^{56}Fe nuclear data

The calculated deviation of $^{32}\text{S}(n,p)^{32}\text{P}$ reaction rate after adjustment has decreased significantly, especially for JEFF-3.3, the maximum deviation has decreased from 26.6% to 1.7%. The agreement of

$^{115}\text{In}(n,n')^{115\text{m}}\text{In}$ has also improved significantly, and all deviations have been reduced to within the error range of the experimental values, with the maximum deviation has decreased from 4.5% to 0.8% for JEFF-3.3 and -5% to -3% for CENDL-3.2. The calculated reaction rate of $^{27}\text{Al}(n,\alpha)^{22}\text{Na}$ shows a bigger deviation after adjustment of the ^{56}Fe nuclear data, but **the calculated deviation still stays within the uncertainty range of the experimental value. The adjustment effect of JEFF-3.3 is better than that of CENDL-3.2, it is believed that this is related to the JEFF-3.3 covariance data. The consistency between the JEFF-3.3 cross section and covariance data produces better adjustment results.**

The accuracy of $^{103}\text{Rh}(n,n')^{103\text{m}}\text{Rh}$ reaction rate based on the adjusted ^{56}Fe nuclear data has not been improved for CENDL-3.2 but presents a slight improvement for JEFF-3.3. It is believed that this is caused by the un-convergence on the sensitivity calculation of $^{103}\text{Rh}(n,n')^{103\text{m}}\text{Rh}$ reaction rate to ^{56}Fe elastic and inelastic cross section. Improved agreements were observed significantly for the reaction rates of $^{197}\text{Au}(n,\gamma)^{198}\text{Au}$, with the maximum deviation has decreased from 13% to 4% for CENDL-3.2 and 15% to 0% for JEFF-3.3. However, there are still several calculated values that exceed the error range of the experimental values. It is believed that this is caused by the un-convergence on the sensitivity calculation to ^{56}Fe elastic and inelastic scattering cross section is much lower than its converged sensitivity to the capture cross section. **Therefore, the $^{197}\text{Au}(n,\gamma)^{198}\text{Au}$ reaction rate can achieve more accuracy adjustment results (due to the capture cross section sensitivity) than the $^{103}\text{Rh}(n,n')^{103\text{m}}\text{Rh}$ reaction rate.**

4.2. validation based on IPPE experiment

Validation of the adjusted ^{56}Fe nuclear data was conducted using the IPPE shielding benchmark experiment. In the IPPE experiment, neutron leakage spectra at 6 different positions were measured, accordingly the validation was conducted by calculating these neutron leakage spectra using the Monte Carlo code. In addition to performing calculations using the adjusted ^{56}Fe nuclear data, calculations based on the ^{56}Fe nuclear data from the latest evaluation of INDEN and the latest evaluation of CNDC were also conducted. For CENDL-3.2, the adjusted results are in good agreement with the latest evaluation results in the range of 200 keV to 5 MeV and after 14 MeV. However, the large deviation at 300 keV still persists, indicating that the cause of this large deviation is not related to the ^{56}Fe nuclear data. **For JEFF-3.3, in the range of 0.1MeV to 1.8 MeV, the calculation results are almost the same before and after adjustment, and in this energy range the results of JEFF-3.3 are better than that of the latest evaluations, from 1.8 MeV to 5MeV, the adjusted results are closer to the latest INDEN evaluation, after 5MeV, the results are consistent before and after the adjustment, but worse than the latest evaluation results.** Figure 6 shows comparison of the IPPE neutron leakage spectrum at 35cm between the calculated values and experimental values.

Figure 6 comparison of calculated results from the latest ^{56}Fe evaluation and the adjusted ^{56}Fe nuclear data

5. CONCLUSION

In this study, JEFF-3.3 and CENDL-3.2 ^{56}Fe nuclear data were adjusted based on shielding experiments ASPIS-Iron88. the ASPIS-Iron88 benchmark was analyzed using the JMCT-2.0 code. Based on the calculated reaction rates and sensitivity coefficients to ^{56}Fe elastic, inelastic and capture cross section, covariances from JEFF-3.3 library, the adjustment of ^{56}Fe nuclear data was carried out. **The ASPIS-Iron88 benchmark was recalculated using the adjustment ^{56}Fe nuclear data, JEFF-3.3 has achieved a better**

adjustment result for ASPIS-Iron88 benchmark which is related to the matching of the covariance data and cross section of JEFF-3.3. Validation based on shielding benchmark experiment IPPE was performed to confirm that calculation accuracy was improved. However, the convergence of sensitivity calculation has a relatively significant impact on the adjustment effect, **in subsequent work, it is still necessary to develop more accurate sensitivity analysis methods.**

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